

DAMAGE MODELLING OF A SATIN SEPCARB[®] COMPOSITE

X. Aubard¹, C. Cluzel^{2,3}, P. Ladevèze² and J.N. Périé²

¹ SEP Division de SNECMA, Le Haillan BP 37, 33165 St MEDARD-EN-JALLES, FRANCE

² LMT Cachan, E.N.S. de Cachan / C.N.R.S. / Univ. P. et M. CURIE, 61 avenue du Président Wilson, 94235 CACHAN Cedex, FRANCE

³ IUT GMP EVRY, Cours Mrg Roméro, 91000 EVRY, FRANCE

SUMMARY: SEP Division de SNECMA manufactures new Carbon/Carbon materials reinforced with an original multidirectional texture. A first series of $[0,90]_n$ satin composite made of non-continuous fibres has been tested. A model written at a mesoscopic scale (ply scale) is used in order to understand and predict the different degradation mechanisms. Experimental results are compared to simulations. New tests using an optical displacement measurement have then been performed on another type of $[0,90]_n$ satin composite. This technique allows estimating strain field heterogeneities and localising degradations. A finite element modelling is finally proposed in order to understand the influence of manufacture onto the mechanical behaviour.

KEYWORDS: Modelling, Damage, Carbon/Carbon, Meso-scale, Micro-cracks closure, Optical strain field measurements, Manufacture simulation.

INTRODUCTION

Sepcarb[®] are Carbon/Carbon composites manufactured by SEP Division de SNECMA. These materials, especially designed for thermo-structural applications, are composed of both a carbon preform and a carbon matrix.

This work deals with modelling the thermo-mechanical behaviour of the plane Multirex[®] family for any in plane complex loading. The temperature influence will be taken into account by an extension of the room temperature models. After recalling the first model described in [3] [4], we focus on further developments involving new performed tests

MATERIAL

Multirex[®] preforms can be plane or axisymmetric. They are obtained by stacking either unidirectional plies or satin layers made of carbon yarns. Yarn fibres can be continuous or non-continuous. A needling process transfers some fibres into the third direction, perpendicular to the layer (see Fig. 1). These fibre reinforcements forbid delamination

propagation. A Chemical Vapour Infiltration (or a similar technique) lays down the matrix into the preform. In this paper, we study satin composites made of non-continuous fibres.

Fig. 1: Manufacture of plane fibrous preform ($[0,90]_n$ satin)

Both tension and compression tests in different directions have been performed on a $[0,90]_n$ satin composite. Loading/unloading cycles allow to separate damage and plastic or viscoplastic responses. Longitudinal and transversal strains are measured using gages. 0° and 90° directions correspond to both fibres directions of the satin. Experimental longitudinal responses of four tests (tension and compression tests at 0° and 45° off axis) are presented Fig. 2. These results reveal:

- an anisotropic behaviour with damage and inelastic strains for tension tests at 0° and 45° off axis;
- a difference of damage evolution between tension and compression for both loading directions.

Fig. 2: Tensile and compressive test at 0° and 45° off axis on a $[0,90]_n$ satin

MODELLING

Fibre reinforcement avoids interface damage propagation. But, because of satin geometry and/or the needling process, fibres are not completely straight. For a high level of this default, a flexion degradation mode appears at the meso level and can lead to local delaminations. A study of the influence of this default on damage for axisymmetric composites made of unidirectional plies is presented in [14] [15] [17].

The difficulty is to define a simple damage kinematics that reproduces the main experimental results for all the composites tested. Damage seems complex to be modelled because of the occurrence of several simultaneous degradation mechanisms. We apply an approach developed in [11] based on:

- anisotropic damage mechanics [10];
- the use of the meso-scale (ply scale) to model the main mechanisms [1];

- the use of simulations to understand how the macroscopic loading is distributed in the different constituents of the tested specimens. Then, we can choose tests leading to dissociate the degradation mechanisms and define an experimental identification method [6].

In a first step, we assume that degradation is anisotropic and dictated by the fibres direction. We consider two mechanisms: a microcracking orthogonal and another parallel to fibres. Therefore, we have applied an anisotropic damage meso-model [11] in the ply coordinate system (1: fibre direction; 2: transversal direction). Two constituents are taken into account: plies composed of continuous fibres and plies composed of non-continuous fibres. For layers composed of continuous fibres, an approach previously implemented for other laminates, such as Carbon/Epoxy [1] or Carbon/Carbon [5], is used herein. For layers composed of non-continuous fibres, an additional damage variable (d_{11}) is introduced in the fibre direction [9]. As shown in [13], such models are able to predict a degradation distribution for the various configurations being tested. Damage kinematics are then described using the strain energy of the damaged layer:

$$E_d = \frac{1}{2} \left\{ \frac{\langle \mathbf{s}_{11} \rangle_+^2}{E_1^0 (1 - d_{11})} + \frac{\langle \mathbf{s}_{11} \rangle_-^2}{E_1^0} + \frac{\langle \mathbf{s}_{22} \rangle_+^2}{E_2^0 (1 - d_{22})} + \frac{\langle \mathbf{s}_{22} \rangle_-^2}{E_2^0} - 2 \frac{\mathbf{n}_{12}^0}{E_1^0} \mathbf{s}_{11} \mathbf{s}_{22} + \frac{\mathbf{s}_{12}^2}{G_{12}^0 (1 - d_{12})} \right\} \quad (1)$$

Damage variables are assumed to be piecewise constant within the different plies. The difference between tension and compression behaviour is attributed to the opening and closure of micro-cracks. This aspect is taken into account by splitting the longitudinal and transversal strain energies into a tension energy ($\langle . \rangle_+$) and a compression energy ($\langle . \rangle_-$).

A complete identification requires subjecting the ply to various loading modes. However, the number of sequences available for each type of material is small. Thus, the identification is limited to the more significant terms of the strain energy [3]. It can be shown that the overall characteristics of composites formed of unidirectional layers are well reproduced by this kind of approach. Other approaches can be found in [2], [8] and [16].

The identification has been achieved in two steps. Elastic coefficients for both meso-constituents have been identified performing tensile tests on $[0,90]_n$ hybrid composites made of both continuous fibres and non-continuous fibres. An extension of this modelling is used to describe satin composite behaviour. Satin plies are firstly approximated by a stacking of two orthogonal unidirectional elementary plies (see Fig. 3) made of non-continuous fibres.

Fig. 3: Modelling of $[0,90]$ satin layers

Non linear coefficients have been identified thanks to tensile tests on this $[0,90]_n$ satin composite made of non-continuous fibres [13].

SIMULATION/TEST COMPARISON

As shown in [3], after an identification procedure, such a model is able to predict a degradation distribution for the different tension tests and for compression test at 0° .

For compression test at 45° off axis, it is shown that the first model does not fit exactly the experimental curves [4] [13]. It appears that the jamming of degradation in the fibre direction is not sufficient to simulate the difference of behaviour between tension and compression. A traction/compression test at 45° shows a modification of elastic stiffness depending on the sign of loading (Fig. 4).

Fig. 4: Compression/tension test at 45° off axis on a $[0,90]_n$ satin

Our conclusion is that another matrix degradation mode occurs: a micro-cracking mechanism orthogonal to the loading direction. A complete set of tests has been achieved on a second type of $[0,90]_n$ satin in order to define an improved model following [12] for carbon/carbon satin composites.

MECHANISMS IDENTIFICATION

To identify the mechanisms responsible for both the non-linear behaviour in tension in the fibre direction and for the difference of behaviour between tension and compression at $\pm 45^\circ$, we performed new tensile tests on a second type of $[0,90]_n$ satin composite made of non-continuous fibres. We used both gages and optical strain field measurements.

The natural material texture allows following surface degradations while measuring strain fields [14]. We took many pictures of one specimen surface while performing the test. By

using a correlation method [15] [17], it is possible to calculate the displacement of many regions of this surface. Lastly the strain field is calculated. In this case, this field information is useful for at least two reasons:

- because the material is porous and pre-cracked, it is rather difficult to observe the degradation evolution. A surface strain field measurement can indicate some regions of interest (see Fig. 5);
- gages located in the same area give different responses. This may indicate that the gage dimension and/or the specimen section are too small in comparison with material defects. Therefore, the results are difficult to interpret without any other information. With this optical technique, it is possible to appreciate the homogeneity of strain fields, at least beneath or near gages (see Fig. 5). This technique can therefore be a good tool to determine gage length when the specimens are large enough.

Fig. 5: Damage location using strain field measurement

For this material, the main features are:

- an elastic behaviour for tensile tests at 0° and 90° ;
- a non-linear behaviour with damage and inelastic strains for tension tests at $\pm 45^\circ$;
- an elastic behaviour for compressive tests at $\pm 45^\circ$ (no damage appears);
- an equivalent maximum failure stress in tension and compression at $\pm 45^\circ$;
- large scatters on failure stresses for the same loading direction;
- some degradation locations occur out of gage regions (See Fig. 5).

The morphology of this $[0,90]_n$ satin composite is very different from the previous one. For example, some significant yarn deflections are observed in contrast to the previous satin composite only small periodic waves are present (satin aspect). These geometrical defects can involve locations and changes of degradation mechanisms [14]. As shown previously, no non-linearities appear when measuring with gages in a “straight” area. But non-linearities appear when using an extensometer (SEP results). For the first type of satin composite, because of the small level of yarn deflection, gage responses are very similar. New tensile test could be performed on this previous material by using the same optical technique. But the region of interest should be smaller.

For composites $[0_y,+45_y,-45_y]_n$ made of unidirectional plies of non-continuous fibres with no major defects, the behaviour is also linear in the fibre direction. Furthermore, we assume that needles can not cut yarns and transfer a small percentage of fibres in the third direction. Thus, non-continuous fibres are not directly responsible for the non-linearities observed in some composites. The origin of these non-linearities may be linked to yarn deflection dependent upon its architecture. The aim of the next section is to address this point.

MANUFACTURE SIMULATION

The needling process (see Fig. 1), by pulling down some fibres, may affect preform properties like the geometry. In order to understand the influence of satin geometry and of needling parameters onto the preform characteristics, we developed a Finite Element model (in CASTEM 2000) of the needling process. In a first step, we consider only one stitch and we assume that only the first ply is affected by needling. We do not consider any yarn transverse deformation [7]. In this model:

- Yarns are circular section beams made of a homogeneous, isotropic and elastic material. Beam quadratic inertia is adjustable in order to represent bending flexibility;
- Fill yarns are straight;
- The satin is balanced.

An initial geometry of a satin stitch is shown Fig. 6.

Fig. 6: FE model of the satin stitch and the base

Contacts can be taken into account by writing distance conditions between beam neutral axes. In the FE modelling, in order to limit problem size, a procedure looks for the nearest nodes and applies the condition only between these nodes.

Because of the loading, the problem is not periodic but a pseudo-periodicity is introduced in the plane directions. Both the inferior layer and the base are represented by a homogeneous, isotropic and elastic media cantilevered at its basis. Contact with the satin is introduced in order to support the satin stitch when loading.

First calculations have been performed in the small perturbation hypothesis. The contact procedure is validated and a first qualitative influence of needling on yarn deflection is obtained (see Fig. 7). An extension to large displacements is under progress to take yarn tension into account. The geometry and the contacts are updated. Friction between yarns is taken into account in order to restrain instabilities. The first results have been obtained for a few yarns.

Fig. 7: FE calculation result for a satin stitch subjected to 4 point displacements

CONCLUSION

A meso-modelling, including damage in fibre direction, is proposed for $[0,90]_n$ satin composites, identified using both an hybrid $[0,90]_n$ (elastic coefficients) and a satin $[0,90]_n$ (non-linear coefficient) and implemented in a simulation software.

For a first type of $[0,90]_n$ satin composite, the main plane characteristics are reproduced and the elastic behaviour is well modelled. Simulations of compression at 45° out of axis reveal a new mechanism.

A second type of $[0,90]_n$ satin composite also made of non-continuous fibres has been tested. No macroscopic damage appears in fibre direction. Qualitative information has been obtained

using an optical strain field measurement. Some important strain heterogeneities are observed. The degradations look like delaminations and appear for high crimp angles.

These observations suggest that the loss of rigidity in fibre direction may be linked to the needling process. A Finite Element model of this procedure has been developed. A satin stitch supported by a flexible base is considered. Calculations have been performed under the small perturbation hypothesis. An extension to large displacements is in progress.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors would like to thank the C.N.E.S. Evry for its financial support.

REFERENCES

- [1] Ladevèze P. and Ledantec E., "Damage modelling of the elementary ply for laminated composites", *Composite Science and Technology*, n° 43, 1992, pp. 257-267.
- [2] Allen D.H., Harris C.E. and Groves S.E., "A Thermomechanical Constitutive Theory for Elastic Composites with Distributed Damage", *International Journal of Solids and Structures*, Vol. 23-9, 1987, pp. 1301-1338.
- [3] Aubard X., Cluzel C., Ladevèze P. and Périé J.N., "Mésomodélisation des matériaux composites carbone/carbone à texture Multirex", *Actes du troisième colloque national en calcul des structures*, Giens, May 20-23, 1997, pp. 863-869.
- [4] Aubard X., Cluzel C., Ladevèze P. and Périé J.N., "Damage meso modelling of a multidirectional Sepcarb®", *Proceedings ICCCE5*, July 5-11 1998 Las Vegas, Ed D. Hui, pp 721-722
- [5] Ladevèze P., O. Allix, C. Cluzel, "Damage modelling at the macro and meso scales for 3D composites" *Damage in Composite Materials*, G. Z. Voyiadjis (Editor), Elsevier Science Publishers B.V., 1993, pp. 195-215.
- [6] Cluzel C., "Méthodologie d'identification mécanique de méso-modèles", *Annales des composites*, JST Interactions modèles expériences dans les composites, 1997.
- [7] Durville D., "Modélisation du comportement mécanique de câbles métalliques", *Actes du troisième colloque national en calcul des structures*, Giens, may 20-23, 1997, pp. 9-22.
- [8] Herakovich C., *Mechanics of Fibrous Composites*, 1997, Wiley J.
- [9] Gasser A., Ladevèze P. and Peres P., "Damage modelling for a laminated ceramic composite", *Materials Science and Engineering*, A250, 1998, pp. 249-255.
- [10] Ladevèze P., "On an anisotropic damage theory", *Failure criteria of structured media*, *Proceedings of the CNRS International Colloquium n° 351*, 1983, Villard de Lans, France, J.P. Boehler Editor, A.A. Balkema Publishers, 1993, pp. 355-365.
- [11] Ladevèze P., "Sur la Mécanique de l'Endommagement des composites", *Proceedings JNC 5*, Ed Bathias & Menkès, Pluralis Publication, Paris, 1986, pp. 667-683.

- [12] Ladevèze P., “Modeling and simulation of the mechanical behavior of CMCs”, *High Temperature Ceramic-Matrix Composite*, Vol. 57, 1995, pp. 53-64.
- [13] Périé J.N. Aubard X., Cluzel C. and Ladevèze P., “Mésomodélisation des mécanismes d’endommagement d’une famille de matériaux Sepcarb® à textures multidirectionnelles”, *Proceedings JNC11*, Arcachon, Nov. 18-20, 1998, pp. 883-888.
- [14] Tardif F., Lamon J. and Berthaud Y., “Analyse des mécanismes d’endommagement sur composites C/C par mesures optiques de déformations”, *JNC11 Arcachon*, Nov. 18-20, 1998, pp. 705-714.
- [15] Collin F., Hild F. and Berthaud Y., “Visualisation par analyse d’images de la répartition des déformations et de l’amorçage dans un matériau composite”, *Photomécanique*, Marne la Vallée, April 14-16, 1998, pp. 241-248.
- [16] Talreja R., “Continuum modelling of damage in ceramic matrix composites”, *Mechanics of materials* 12, 1991, pp. 165-180.
- [17] Mguil S., Morestin F. and Brunet M., “Mesure des déformations par corrélation directe d’images numériques”, *Photomécanique*, Marne la Vallée, April 14-16, 1998, pp. 361-368.